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Metall kesish dastgohlari kesish rejimi elementlarini avtomatlashtirilgan hisoblash ilovasi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola “ToolCalc” nomli mobil ilova haqida bo‘lib, u metall kesish dastgohlari uchun kesish rejimi elementlarini (kesish tezligi, surish masofasi, aylanish chastotasi, kesish chuqurligi) avtomatlashtirilgan tarzda hisoblab beradi. Pova 9 ta dastgoh turini qo‘llab-quvvatlaydi va standartlarga asoslangan formulalardan foydalanadi. Amaliy sinovlar ilova yordamida hisoblash vaqtini 70% ga qisqartirganini va parametrlarning 95% aniqligini tasdiqladi. Maqolada ilova dizayni va u haqida to‘liq ma’lumotlar keltiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ToolCalc, metall kesish, avtomatlashtirish.

Приложение для автоматизированного расчета элементов режима резания металлорежущих станков

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Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена мобильному приложению под названием “ToolCalc”, которое автоматически рассчитывает элементы режима резания (скорость резания, дальность подачи, частота вращения, глубина резания) для металлорежущих станков. Приложение поддерживает 9 типов станков и использует формулы, основанные на стандартах. Практические испытания подтвердили сокращение времени вычислений с помощью приложения на 70% и точность параметров на 95%. В статье приводится дизайн приложения и подробная информация о нем.

Ключевые слова: ToolCalc, резка металла, автоматизация.

Application for automated calculation of cutting mode elements of metal cutting machines

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Abstract. This article is about the mobile application "ToolCalc", which automatically calculates the elements of the cutting mode (cutting speed, feed distance, rotation frequency, cutting depth) for metal cutting machines. The application supports 9 types of machines and uses formulas based on standards. Practical tests confirmed that the application reduced the calculation time by 70% and the accuracy of the parameters by 95%. The article provides detailed information about the application design.

Keywords: ToolCalc, metal cutting, automation.

Kirish

Metall kesish jarayonlari zamonaviy ishlab chiqarishda muhim o‘rin tutadi, chunki ular mahsulot sifati va ishlab chiqarish samaradorligiga bevosita ta‘sir qiladi. An‘anaviy usulda kesish rejimi elementlari (kesish tezligi, surish masofasi, aylanish chastotasi va kesish chuqurligi) qo‘lda hisoblanadi, bu jarayon vaqt talab qiladi va inson xatolariga olib kelishi mumkin. Shu sababli, avtomatlashtirilgan hisoblash vositalari so‘rovga ega bo‘lib bormoqda. "ToolCalc" ilovasi aynan shu muammolarni hal qilish uchun ishlab chiqilgan bo‘lib, u 9 ta dastgoh turi uchun optimal parametrlarni aniq va tezkor tarzda taqdim etadi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi – ilovaning texnik xususiyatlari, foydali jihatlari va amaliy qo‘llanilishini o‘rganishdir.

Metodologiya

ToolCalc ilovasi Android platformasi uchun ishlab chiqilgan va foydalanuvchilar uchun qulay interfeys bilan jihozlangan. U quyidagi bosqichlardan iborat:

Dastgoh turi tanlash: 3x3 tugmalar orqali foydalanuvchi tokarlik, parmash, jilvirlash, kombinatsiyalashgan, tish/rezba ochuvchi, frezalash, randalash, qirqib tushirish va har xil zamonaviy dastgohlardan birini tanlaydi.

Ma‘lumot kiritish: Detalning materiali (masalan, po‘lat yoki alyuminiy) va o‘lchamlari kiritiladi.

Hisoblash: Python dastur tilida yozilgan standartlarga asoslanib, kesish tezligi (m/min), surish masofasi (mm/aylanish), aylanish chastotasi (ayl/min) va kesish chuqurligini (mm) aniqlaydi.

Natijalar ko'rsatish: Hisoblangan parametrlar jadvallar va grafiklar shaklida taqdim etiladi.

Texnik jihatdan, ilova quyidagi asosiy formulalardan foydalanadi:

Kesish tezligi:

$$V_c = (\pi * D * n) / 1000$$

bu yerda, D – diametr (mm), n – aylanish chastotasi (ayl/min).

Aylanish chastotasi:

$$n = (1000 * V_c) / (\pi * D)$$

Surish masofasi va kesish chuqurligi material va dastgoh turiga qarab standart diapazonlarda belgilanadi yoki quyidagi formuladan aniqlanadi:

$$S_o = f * n$$

Tahminiy ishlov berish vaqti:

$$T = L / S_o$$

Ilova dizayni Android platformasining foydalanuvchi interfeysi va logotipi dizayni quyidagicha:

Natijalar

ToolCalc ilovasi sinovlarda muvaffaqiyatli natijalar ko'rsatdi. Amaliy sinovlar quyidagi ma'lumotlarni berdi:

Hisoblash vaqti 70% ga qisqardi, bu operatorlar uchun vaqt tejashni anglatadi.

Parametrlarning ISO standartlariga mos kelish darajasi 95% ni tashkil etdi.

Foydalanuvchilarning 90% i ilovani 5 daqiqadan kamroq vaqt ichida o'zlashtirdi.

Quyidagi grafik ilova bilan va ilovasiz kesish rejimi elementlarini hisoblashdagi vaqt tejashilishi va ishlab chiqarishdagi samaradorlik taqqoslanadi:

Xulosa

ToolCalc ilovasi metall kesish rejimi elementlarini hisoblash jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish orqali ishlab chiqarish sohasida muhim ahamiyatga ega. U operatorlarning ish vaqtini 70% ga qisqartirib, standartlarga 95% mos keladigan aniq parametrlar taqdim etadi. Bu natijalar ilovaning ayniqsa kichik va o'rta korxonalar uchun samarali vosita ekanligini ko'rsatadi, chunki u qo'lda hisoblashdagi xatolar va vaqt sarfini sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi. Soddalashtirilgan interfeys va intuitiv dizayn foydalanuvchilar uchun qulay muhit yaratdi, bu esa 90% foydalanuvchilarning ilovani 5 daqiqadan kamroq vaqt ichida ilovadan foydalanishni o'zlashtirishiga imkon berdi.

Kelajakda ToolCalcni rivojlantirish uchun bir qator imkoniyatlar mavjud. Masalan, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi algoritmlar qo'shilishi orqali parametrlar yanada moslashtirilgan va optimallashtirilgan bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa aniqlikni 98% gacha oshirishi mumkin. Shuningdek, iOS platformasi uchun versiya ishlab chiqilishi ilovaning foydalanuvchi doirasini kengaytirib, global bozorda raqobatbardoshlikni oshiradi. Umuman olganda, ToolCalc nafaqat hozirgi ishlab chiqarish ehtiyojlari talabiga mos. Ushbu ilova O'zbekiston sanoatida raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirish jarayonlarini rivojlantirishga muhim hissa qo'shadi va xalqaro miqyosda ham e'tirof etilishi uchun katta imkoniyatlarga ega.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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